

REVIVAL OF TRADITIONAL TURKISH & MEVLEVI MUSIC

Changes in Turkish Classical and Sufi Music in the 20th Century

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Turkish music, in the previous centuries, has gone through radical changes. These changes were a combination of political and religious influences. Hence to assist those in Turkey who are trying to reconnect with their traditional music, this paper examines the roots and the changes in the way which music is played in Turkey.

Most of the information in this paper is taken from "The Music of Rumi" the book which contains all the research from my doctorate in the "Philosophy of Music". A doctorate based on actual experience and decades of teaching through the meşk system related to traditional Turkish and Mevlevi music. (Sufi music).

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Introduction

This paper traces the history of the Traditional Turkish Art Music played in current 21st century Turkey. Music in the Anatolian plateau and the part of Turkey which is on the European side of the Bosphorus, has a fascinating history. This history cannot be separated from the effects of any religion and/or politics dominant throughout the history of this interesting part of the world.

Due to the effects of the three seas, Mediterranean sea, Black sea and Caspian sea, the Anatolian part of Turkey's mainland has become the area which acted as a joining part for Eastern Europe with the Middle East and India. Trade, culture, wars and religion have passed through this part of the world in a constant stream throughout the many centuries of settled communities existing in the area.

According to finds made in the last 60 years or more within the archaeological site at Çatalhöyük South-East of Konya, settled communities have existed in this area for more than 9,000 years. A site further to the East at Göbekli Tepe reveals a structure which is clearly some kind of temple for worship. This site has been dated as 1,000 years earlier than the one at Çatalhöyük. The Göbekli Tepe site shows that some kind of religion existed all those centuries ago, yet so far there is no evidence that music was used there. Yet to have constructed such a place for worship, the community must have been settled.

So we know that settled communities and religion (most likely with music) have existed in Anatolia for a very long time. Music is as natural to human beings as it is to many animals and birds. The Bhagavad Gita has been chanted to a very musical melody for many thousands of years using only the human voice. If ancient Anatolians only used the voice for music we would not expect to find much evidence of this. With musicians in their communities they would easily adopt music from a migrating community or from a traveller who imported music from another culture; such as Pythagoras did.

During my last visit to Konya in October 2024 I observed a willingness to revive the authentic approach to the traditional music of 100 or more years ago. Hence this paper attempts to trace the type and use of music in Turkey so as to assist those who are making

a 21st century attempt to revive the use of musical scales (Makams) used in the Traditional Art Music of Turkey and the Sufi music; and taught to me through meşk (meshk).

The Wider Picture

Music in an advanced form is known to have existed at least 5,000 years ago in Egypt. The flute used at that time is no different to the reed flute called the 'ney' as used in Turkey today. There are numerous wall paintings found in Egypt which depict a wide range of instruments used during their ancient civilisation. Yet after the immense amount of archaeology which has been carried out, no evidence of the notes played has been found. (i.e. musical notation or theory). Other than the frets on the Tanbur below. In my way of thinking this is an error of archaeological thought; projecting 20th century ideas onto past civilisations.

Ney player depicted in the tomb of Nenkhef 3,000 BC

Egyptian Tanbur wall painting. Tomb of Nebmun 1,350 BC

Let me give a clue as to how I have come to the above conclusion. After much study by a researcher from the USA into the players of the ancient flute music of Japan, the researcher tried to get the flautists to play their music from a very clever system of notation which he had devised. They considered his idea and responded with a simple statement which he did not really anticipate - **"We cannot understand how you expect us to learn music through the eyes."**

Music is an aural art, meaning we only need ears to know all about it and reproduce it. The American had not seen this.

My mother could not read music notation, yet she played the piano like a professional. If she heard a new song on the radio, she could sit at the piano and play the song perfectly using her left hand to give accompaniment to the melody of the right hand. When I first heard her do this I was amazed. The Japanese flautists did not need their music written down. Music is not learned through the visual sense, hence Egyptian notations or writings about how to play their music would not be necessary; meaning oral tradition was most likely the means of teaching; or meşk as once used throughout Turkey.

Also many musicians in Turkey may not know two of the facts stated above. Firstly that the ney (flute) was played in Egypt 5,000 years ago. And secondly, that a little more than a hundred years ago most Turkish musicians did not play music from notations. Neither did they need books of written music theory if they had an oral tradition to follow. This was called meşk (meshk) in Turkey and was banned in the 1920s so as to make way for European style music academies; called **"teaching civilised music"**. European music has for centuries veered towards the use of notation.

The power of the human memory in respect of music was demonstrated to me by my principal music teacher tanbur virtuoso Necdet Yaşar during the 1980's, when for more than a decade he taught me more than 70 of the Makams of traditional Turkish music (all on record). For each Makam he played two or three well known classical pieces. He never referred to notations and he played the pieces 100% perfectly. This shows he had 200 compositions in his memory, at least. Nezih Uzel a teacher, Sufi and great friend of mine, knew many Sufi Ilahiler (hymns) without any need for notations; this means poetry and music. Among his followers some estimated the number into 1,000s.

I should add to the above that Necdet Yaşar often explained in detail to me where the current (20th century) music practice was incorrect in terms of intervals; And where the theory books in use by Turkish musicians were incorrect in understanding Makams and

their traditional construction. Necdet knew all the correct ways of playing and all the incorrect ways as well. He demonstrated both ways on the Tanbur, with explanations.

We must keep the above facts in mind while reading this paper. And consider that the existence of the Göbekli Tepe temple means that music was probably used in rituals; and that we would not expect to find much evidence of this. Because 10,000 years is long enough for any instruments to have decayed completely and for any other evidence to have been eradicated by the effects of time. As with Egypt, lack of such evidence is itself **not** proof that music was not a part of the religious culture of Göbekli Tepe.

It's a long story for another time, but I could easily demonstrate that the human being is created with all the numbers and ratios required for the system of music which Pythagoras used. Hence music is natural to human beings. See "The Music of Rumi".

The Effect of the Greeks and Arabs

The Greek civilisation, dating from 3,200 years ago (1,200 BC), not only occupied all the lands which are now Turkey, but they also conquered the Middle East; and later on (322 BC) the Egyptian Pharaohs. But this was not before the man known as Pythagoras had lived in the Egyptian temples for at least a decade (approx. 535 BC); when the temples were still in possession of a great musical heritage. The Egyptians at that time recognised the spiritual development of Pythagoras such that he was accepted into their inner circle. We do not have any record of what he discovered there, but we can be sure that music was a part of the life in the temples, from the many wall paintings which have survived.

Pythagoras also studied philosophy in India. He became a great teacher there and was known as Pitha Guru, which means 'father teacher'. This seems to be the origin of the sound of his name known to us today; pitha = Pytha and guru = goras; Pytha+goras. He may also have studied music in India or Tibet. See more details on page 15.

It was Pythagoras who brought music scales to the European part of the world. The many modes such as Ionian, Dorian, Phrygian, Lydian, etc. are the basis of early European music; the tetrachords and pentachords which they contain originated from the Pythagoreans. It would seem this knowledge may have come from Egypt and/or India.

The great Turkish musicologist and Mevlevi, Rauf Yekta Bey, researched the origins of Turkish music up to the time he was living; I had his lengthy treatise translated to English for me, from French. He was very clear in his discoveries, that the writings of the Greeks (lost to themselves) were preserved in the Arabic speaking lands of the once time Greek empire area of the Middle East. These writings were by great Arabic speaking musicologists such as Al Kindi, Al Farabi, Ibn Sina and Safi Al Din. These men were not only musicians they were also great philosophers. They recognised and utilised all the musical methods of Pythagoras; and connected it with spirituality. The Pythagorean use of music for healing human ailments was utilised by the Seljuks and the Ottomans in their Darüşşifas (healing establishments). They knew which Makams would heal particular ailments. This practice had gone on for thousands of years since the times of Pythagoras.

Around the world great philosophers recognise the works and findings of all other great philosophers throughout history. This they do with no barriers of race or religion standing in their way. This is because their inner view of human life has risen above all divisions which arise through nationality, language and religion. Rauf Yekta Bey was such a man, as were all Mevlevi Sheikhs and Mevlevi holy men; and of course Mevlana.

My book "The Music of Rumi" is my own attempt to emulate those of my much greater predecessors. [*"If I have seen further it is by standing on the shoulders of Giants."* Sir Isaac Newton (1675).] We are nothing without our esteemed predecessors. Every day remember all your teachers; such remembering may bring the much needed humility.

The Effect of the Modern Europeans

Above it is clear that in our time it is the effect of the Greeks and the Arabic speaking peoples which has preserved a system of music which has magical properties, such that, despite the effects of time to erode all things to nothing, we can still have the knowledge of ancient music; if we keep to the Pythagorean intervals and not alter them to suit European music methods. The system taught to me is the legacy of ancient Pythagorean music.

Taking away the important finer intervals needed in Pythagorean music is the same as extracting all the essential nutrients in the food we eat; and then expecting to be nourished by it. The food may look the same, but it will not give that essential nourishment. Likewise music deficient in microtones will not connect to the soul in the way Pythagoras designed it to do. A childhood exposed exclusively to tempered scales does not need to be a barrier to understanding the natural music of Pythagoras. I am a living example of this fact. I played piano, guitar and studied only European classical music as a young man.

Let me give the example of a different subject to clarify the musical loss described above. Jesus (Issa) most certainly studied Vedanta philosophy in India. There is too much evidence of this for the fact to be refuted; evidence both in historic records and in the identical nature of His teaching with that of Vedanta. Vedanta has full recognition of the continued incarnation of each human soul (called reincarnation); and the law of karma which goes with it. Hence for Jesus to be true to the teaching which He knew he included knowledge of these two things (reincarnation and the law of karma) to His close followers. The formal Christian doctrine from Rome included knowledge of reincarnation and karma for 500 years after Jesus. But due to the inconvenience of accepting it (i.e. future punishment being unavoidable - karma), the 6th century Empress Theodora had the knowledge and discussion of these things made into a heresy (i.e. made illegal). Christian doctrine was enforced by the state, with severe punishment for those who went against it. Hence after banning the doctrine of reincarnation and karma, all future generations would not get the benefit from it. This benefit is manifold and includes the absence of stress and sorrow arising from death of the physical body; and why adverse things happen in life.

Origen the great holy 3rd century Christian theologian, stated that :- **“Jesus taught the human soul originated in God and was returning to Him through the lessons of many incarnations.”** Theodora may have controlled society but not Mother Nature. How is it politicians think they can pass a law to abolish things as permanent as the moon?

It is now almost impossible to convince a modern Christian that the human soul will return and continue its progress in another human body. Such is the effect of centuries of a belief system which was altered for convenience. Other associated religions may also have this deficiency; it is due to attachment to the physical body. The soul can never die.

Here we have a similar situation where for political convenience a music tradition has had essential elements removed, which has the potential to deprive all future generations of the benefit which those missing elements can provide. Now a hundred years since Pythagorean Makams were corrupted by state decree, means most people in Turkey have a false conception of what Makams originally sounded like. Turkey was the custodian of a valuable and rich heritage of mankind. Politics had no authority to corrupt or ban it.

We must not let such things as “westernisation” destroy this legacy of music. The ignorance of the Europeans has gone around the world for many centuries, with a view to making monetary wealth, theft of treasures and trade. And in this process have not respected the established and ancient traditions of those nations which they conquered.

It is unfortunate that in the last century Turkey has not recognised this damage done by the unspiritual Europeans. And instead Turkey has sought to emulate their ways, which are substantially materialistic. The 20th century development of music in Europe

has moved away from the true spiritual way towards the ways of power, wealth and pleasure; such things which great spiritual teachers advise against. Hence, the European massive orchestras with many simultaneous melodies and notes, and the need for a conductor. All to produce what? As if bigger is better. Sound volumes are so high in many large orchestras that many performers suffer hearing loss over time; ruining their career in music. It is an ignorant European way of creating music which is supposed to have a better effect. Enjoyable maybe, but not spiritual in the way ancient music was.

I saw two Turkish musicians enthral hundreds of people with only a Tanbur and Ney at an international music festival in Durham, northern UK. They were all spiritually lifted.

Turkey has a rich spiritual heritage through its religion and through the Sufi traditions, which predate even Christianity. Now is the time for Turkey to make the best attempt to turn the clock back to a time when its music carried the original inspiration of its ancestors; and the legacy they had from those mentioned above.

How Did the Music Survive in Turkey Under Islam?

There is little doubt that music was openly allowed when Turkey was a Christian country. Music was used in many ways within the Christian church. Which kind of music is not clear as there naturally are no recordings of their performances. We cannot look to Europe for clues because it is clear that the European Christians have both mixed their music with the indigenous music of the countries they converted and have also altered their music through the use of tempered scales; as the final nail in the coffin of true music.

Under the rules of Islam the permission to use music is not clear. Different interpretations of the rules will give a “yes” or a “no” depending on the fancy of the leader of the day. Hence there were times when all music was banned in Turkey under Ottoman Sultans. And in one era this included the sema ritual of the Mevlevi and other Sufi orders. I remember during discussions with the Istanbul Mevlevi, into whom I was accepted, they mentioned that previous bans on their Sema and music had occurred during the history of the Mevlevi tradition. It was their hope then (1980s) that the current ban, which commenced in the 1920s, would also be lifted, as it had been in previous centuries. Hence they were keeping their tradition fully alive, in which I shared, in private homes, in defiance of the law; yet it was not to be (read my document “Mevlevi Music and Whirling” on academia.edu). The current musical/whirling event is not Mevlevi.

Hence if religion had been successful during the Ottoman times then the practise of music, as we know it in Turkey may not have survived. To ban a subject which makes no sound is difficult to enforce. But music is easy to detect, since houses of olden times were not really soundproof. I remember once when making a sema to live music in the Mevlevi Çelebi’s home, that a neighbour alerted the police who then came to the house, but were sent away. Yet such places as the Yenikapı Tekke, built outside the Istanbul city walls in 1597, was such a place that could defy any ban. It is likely that at that time the choice to build a Tekke so far from the city centre, was connected with being free from any restrictions imposed by religious leaders or Sultans. Any visitor or Sultan’s authority which came near their semahane (ceremony room) would be known; and measures could be taken to stop any music being played, or divert the visitor away; so as not to attract prosecution. Hence it is not surprising that the Yenikapı Tekke (Dergah) became the hub for Turkey’s greatest musicians and composers; and the most inspired Mevlevi Ayins.

As Yenikapı was my Sheikh’s Tekke (Resuhi Baykara) I visited it every time I went to Istanbul. Polis, who was the custodian of the gate, would always open it for me; as I often met him at Resuhi Baykara’s home, hence he knew me. After the third fire there in 1997, due to squatters, it was the last straw for me. I spoke to Nezhil Uzel mentioning that it was an important part of Turkey’s heritage and should be restored. Nezhil was very well

known and respected in Istanbul. The next year he told me that a group of people were raising funds to restore the Yenikapı Tekke. It was completed in 2012. It is now used as a University. But the rebuilt Semahane is used for Mevlevi Sema. I went to a Sema there.

Hence due to such places as Yenikapı the traditional music of Turkey was certainly continued at the time of any religious or political ban on its practise; giving the Sufis the role of protector of this great musical heritage. History shows that the courts of the Sultans were frequented by the Mevlevi musicians and that traditional classical music was developed there with the assistance of the great Mevlevi composers in conjunction with other Turkish musicians. Above is the effect of politics, religion and that of the Sufis on the traditional music of Turkey.

What Was in Their Music That the Sufis Knew and Preserved?

Anyone who has the fortune to be a musician in the performance of an authentic Mevlevi Ayin (ritual music), performed with the Pythagorean intervals intended by the composer, would know the answer to the above question; (authentic means used in the Tekkes prior to being closed). But this possibility was taken away from Turkey due to the westernisation of their traditional music as mentioned above. The following sections are an attempt to describe the answer with minimal music theory.

All Mevlevi Ayins played in Turkey today are not the true intention of the composers, due to lack of the correct intervals taught to me by Necdet Yaşar, Turkey's acknowledged master of the Makam system. He spent many hours during many visits to his home (all on record) teaching me and my daughter how to decipher the code of the transposed Makams in the Mevlevi Ayins, taken from the notations which had survived.

During the decades (1980s and 1990s) that I scoured Istanbul for notations from a wide range of sources, I have discovered at least five different persons who took the trouble to notate the Ayin melodies. Most of these, some hand written, were from either being present at the Ayin performance or from recordings of the Ayin. Also each person used different notation systems for the transcriptions. Hence I had to study the various notation systems so as to understand the intentions of the scribe. For most of the Ayins I have three different sources; some more, some less. Necdet Yaşar knew all the Mevlevi Ayins and he knew what Makams were in the various parts of the compositions. Mevlevi music is the most complex in terms of changing Makams and transposing Makams. With the training and teaching which Necdet gave and many years of work in arriving at the Makams and transposed Makams in each Ayin, my daughter and I have begun to finalise, what we believe is the correct way that each Ayin was intended by the composers. Some use complex transpositions. It is a truly Sherlock Holmes type of detective work. For this purpose I have invented an innovative notation system which indicates Makam tetra-chords and pentachords used in the music. (see my book "The Music of Rumi.")

After the lengthy process of the doctorate, it independently verified that the meşk system as taught by Necdet Yaşar was true to the Pythagorean tradition in relation to Makams. I made many discoveries during that process which I will try to summarise here. The doctorate was called "The Philosophy of Music". Hence get ready for a philosophical look at the music of the Pythagoreans. This music is liquid philosophy.

How is the Human Soul Able to Experience Music?

The Pythagoreans envisioned the relationship of the human soul to the physical world as having a joining function shown diagrammatically opposite → Here the "demiurge" is an intermediary between the Creator and the universe. In my view this demiurge is the same

as the god Brahma in the Vedanta philosophy. In that ancient philosophy the Creator (Brahman) is not allowed to take part in the process of creation. His nature is immutable, hence He might lose that if He were to get involved in action. Hence the philosophy creates various “minor” gods who carry out the process of creation; philosophically allowing the Creator to be free of action. In the Greek view shown by the above diagram the world is contained within the soul. This really means that their view is that the world is an expression of the soul. This is true from the demiurge point of view. But not the way we see it from our point of view, as embodied beings. (i.e. the demiurge is not embodied).

Hence we need a view from the way we experience life; hence I have devised a diagram to avoid too many words. This shows our human life as we live it. We know we have a physical body and mind. Also there is one who experiences through the mind; the one who watches. This one is termed soul and is said in philosophy to have the same nature as the Creator.

THE TRIADIC STRUCTURE OF THE HUMAN

But we know that the adjacent pairs here need to be connected to each other. Body connects to the mind with the five senses of hearing, touch, sight, taste and smell. Without these senses the mind would have no experience or knowledge of the world. Likewise the soul (the one who watches) would also have no experience of the world, unless there were a connection with the mind. This one I designate as the intellect. It is where memory also resides and the ability to make connections between various aspects of the information brought to it through the senses and the mind. Intellect is a vital part of the human being.

THE FIVE-FOLD NATURE OF THE HUMAN

We need to realise that only part (C) can be fully studied scientifically. This is due to the subtle nature of the other parts which do not show up on physical instruments. Electrical impulses in the physical brain are only the attempt to transfer information to the mind. They are not the mind itself. With this view we now have a complete path for the inner consciousness to pass from the realm beyond the soul (A) to the physical body (C). This enables us to experience the world. We can study this diagram only within ourselves.

This now generates four areas of overlap where two parts are joined. Where the senses overlap in the physical body is where the sense organs are located. These organs gather information to impress it on the mind. The senses themselves are very subtle and cannot be studied by scientific instruments. The mind, intellect and soul even more so.

The four overlap areas show us the basic parts of what it means to be human. This diagram is a simple way all the parts can be shown to relate to each other. It is a diagram of the way our experience of the world works; which is registered within the soul.

How does all this relate to music? In the tradition of the ancient music system it is stated that a musician has four basic areas where s/he needs to achieve mastery. That means for the full expression of the magic in the Makams the musician needs to be a master of these four aspects of musical performance. These four are:-

1. Mastery of the instrument of choice.
2. To be a master of the Makam system.
3. To master the communication with other musicians and audience.
4. Mastery of communication within oneself; includes intuition.

These four would come approximately in order of time. It is only possible to master the Makam system when an instrument has been mastered. Likewise communication with other musicians is only possible when the Makam system has been mastered. Hence there is a natural order of these four, as each originates from deeper within our psyche.

At this point let's see how the Makams were realised originally. In the legend of the life of Pythagoras we have the following tale, presumably at some time related by Pythagoras himself to his followers when teaching them music.

"Pythagoras related that his Soul rose as far as the higher world. Due to the purity of his being and to the divinatory power of his heart, he heard the melodies of the Spheres and the sonorities produced by the movements of the heavenly bodies; at the same time he became aware of the discreet resonance of the voices of their Angels." ¹ (for me, Makams are these voices)

Here it is clear that the Makams were a result of a deeply spiritual experience which we cannot easily understand. Hence in the tradition started by Pythagoras he set a formula which would assist musicians to come closer to the experience which he had. This involves the four part mastery described above. Hence I have modified the above diagram to show how the return to the experience of Pythagoras maybe made possible.

Here I can explain the logic of the position of the four goals of mastery; each stage of mastery taking us deeper within our experience of music; leading us closer to the soul.

1. Mastery of an instrument involves mainly the use of hands, fingers; with the ears and eyes playing an important role. Hence it is located at the body/senses junction; where our attention involves mainly physical and sense combination.
2. Knowledge of the Makams (science of music) involves the sense of sound with the sense impressions coming to the mind. The accuracy in being able to hear the microtones is related to the sharpness of the player's mental listening powers. This involves mainly paying attention to the sense impressions which come to the mind.
3. Communication with other musicians is using both the mind and intellect in knowing or sensing (mentally) the tempo and the intentions of the other musicians. It requires creativity. If items 1 & 2 are mastered then there is space in the mind and intellect to connect with others in the same room. This can include the audience. If items 1 & 2 are not mastered then the musician will be mentally

¹ Godwin J () Music, Mysticism and Magic : London : Penguin Group

occupied with making sure the correct notes are played and that the correct feel of the Makam is being invoked. Hence there will be less attention available for communicating with others. Each part includes the ones previous to it.

4. Communication within oneself is clearly a personal requirement of having studied and practised the art of invoking one's own intuition and allowing the soul to express its purity through the chosen Makam. This is developed with the art of Taksim (improvisation) which is a test for the functioning of intuition.

Here we can see how the natural order of progress of the Pythagorean musician can be portrayed in a diagrammatic way. And it shows us that as the musician progresses s/he needs to explore deeper levels of being as the four parts are slowly mastered in the order shown here. This was the training given by Pythagoras to his students; and the training given to me through the meşk system by Necdet Yaşar. I did my best as his student.

The Intervals Used in Makam Science

Pythagoras was a master mathematician. To him the whole creation is mathematical. Hence he applied the natural occurrence of number in the purest and simplest way. This was to accord with the nature of the human soul. He noted that the voice of a woman, when asked to imitate the note sung by a man, would actually be a higher pitch than the man's. This he discovered was actually double the vibrations of the man's note. Hence he designated it as the first harmony of musical tones. This is a ratio of 2:1. The man's note was half the pitch of the woman's; later called the octave.

Extending this simple principle, using a monochord instrument, he explored the natural series of intervals where one number is a single digit higher than the other. Hence we have the following sequence:- 2:1; 3:2; 4:3; 5:4; 6:5 and so on; which he used.

Another interesting observation made by the mathematical genius of Pythagoras, is that where the ratios 3:2 and 4:3 are added (perfect 5th added to perfect 4th) the ratio of 2:1 is arrived at. These first three intervals (2:1; 3:2 and 4:3) he decided would form the basic building blocks of melody. He extended this idea into the next two on the list (5:4 and 6:5) and discovered that they are equal to the perfect 5th (3:2). This concept can be extended throughout the range. Shown here only as far as 16:15; but it does continue.

He also noted that the perfect fifth interval (3:2) added to the octave (2:1) was also a harmonious sounding interval. Its ratio is (2:1) x (3:2) is 3:1. Hence he was sure to examine the sequence 5:3; 7:5; 9:7; 11:9 etc.: another natural sequence. He found many of these intervals had a mysterious effect on the listeners. This is because no even numbers are used to create them, creating effects within the psyche and hence the physical body. The same logic of inclusion applies to the range with only odd numbers, but three intervals.

Hence Pythagoras formed a full range of intervals which he could play with, so as to discover the best way to utilise them for the art and science of music. All these intervals were tested to discover which sounded musical and would fit as either three intervals or four intervals within the space of a perfect 4th (4:3) or a perfect 5th (3:2); his basic blocks.

At some time in history it was discovered that when the octave (2:1) is divided into 53 equal intervals then exact numbers of these small intervals (called commas) would fit many of those two ranges of intervals shown above (even:odd and odd:odd). Comma numbers are useful in teaching the system, as they avoid too much mathematics. Combining intervals and the comma idea we have a full table finally used by Pythagoras after he eliminated those intervals which were not suitable for use as music. This determination was made with the quote made on page 8 above, from J. Godwin's book "Music, Mysticism and Magic" as his guidance. Rauf Yekta Bey in his treatise on Turkish music, details this process very thoroughly. Here is the table of intervals used.

Odd and Even numbers			Odd numbers only		
Ratio	Exact Commas	No. used	Ratio	Exact Commas	No. used
2:1	53	53	3:1	84	84
3:2	31	31	5:3	39.06	39
4:3	22	22	7:5	25.72	26
5:4	17.06	17	9:7	19.22	19 ½
6:5	13.94	14	11:9	15.34	15 ½
7:6	11.79	12	13:11	12.77	13
9:8	9.01	9	15:13	10.94	11
10:9	8.06	8	23:21	6.96	7
15:14	5.28	5	25:23	6.38	6 ⅓
16:15	4.93	5	27:25	5.88	6
19:18	4.13	4	31:29	5.10	5
20:19	3.92	4	39:37	4.02	4
77:76	1.0	1	this range discovered in my research		

The task Pythagoras set himself was to find which groups of notes forming either perfect 4ths or perfect 5ths would be beneficial to both players and listeners. Hence we see that the intervals 8:7; 11:10 etc. are missing from the table. Similarly there are intervals from the "odds only" list which are not used. He also included those which could heal human ailments. The final list was used to create several of groups of three, called tetrachords and groups of four called pentachords. Compare this to the 8 European intervals available to them. Viz:- 84, 53, 31, 22, 18, 13, 9 & 4.5.

There were found to be many groups which could create musical melody. A typical example is the one now called Rast tetrachord.

In whichever way these four notes are used in music it is impossible to find a combination which is dissonant. The same applies to the pentachord formed by adding a whole tone (9:8) to the upper note.

Hence other tetrachords and pentachords can be created by moving the group of intervals shown into a different order. The tetrachords now called Usshak and Segah are examples of this. None of these can be correctly played using tempered scales of notes.

Integrating the intervals from the odds only list created the mysterious tetrachords which create the magic in Sufi music. It is likely that Pythagoras kept this range secret, as there is no documentary evidence of it. Yet my Sherlock Homes approach did discover them during the doctorate process. A full analysis and explanation of all these matters can be found in my doctorate book called "The Music of Rumi" which contains all things explained in this paper and much more. Get your free copy (original price UK£65).

A copy of this book will only cost you the postage to your address or your university. Contact me on alan.prosser@btinternet.com You will be invoiced through PayPal. After posting, for confidentiality and security reasons, name and address will not be retained. Current postage to Turkey (Nov. 2024) from UK = UK£15 . (approx. ₺ 675).

There is one more aspect of intervals. It is how they relate to all the matters mentioned above in their numerical aspect. For this we need to consider the ability of the four functional overlap areas shown above. For this I developed another diagram.

Empirical Application of Interval Ranges

Sense Organs: -- range 2:1 to 4:3 and 3:1 to 9:7 ; these are the larger intervals i.e. the octave + perfect 5th and the octave, perfect 5th and perfect 4th; with others of similar size range. Most people would know immediately if these larger intervals were out of tune; almost without focussing the attention on the mental impressions. They are the basic range for the tuning of any musical instrument.

Sense Impressions: -- ranges 5:4 to 16:15 and 11:9 to 27:25 ; the musical thirds, whole tones and semi-tones. This range is the basic difference between hearing and listening. They require the engagement of the mind with the sense impressions, so that they can be distinguished accurately. It is necessary to hear the difference between those that are close to each other, so that the art of Makam Science can be mastered.

Creativity: -- ranges 17:16 to 64:63 and 29:27 to 81:79; smaller intervals down to one comma size; not all used directly in Makam construction, but to be able to distinguish them is necessary for playing in tune with other musicians; because some Makams have differences which depend on these small differences; the important range for creativity in music. Discernible to the well trained musician. The level of being of the musician is raised by contact with hearing or producing these interval sizes.

The above two ranges contain the 4 comma (limma) which is vital in the appreciation of modal music and does not occur at all in music using equal temperament. See the book "The Music of Rumi" for a more detailed analysis of this subject.

Intuition: -- interval ranges 65:64 to 256:255 & 83:81 to 243:241; which includes 1.86 commas to 0.3 commas and represents the "inner inner octave" of musical intervals. These go to the limit of the perceptible range of the normal sense of hearing as perceived through the medium of air. When intervals are on the border of human perception they move into the realm of feeling the difference rather than hearing it. This is how they evoke deeper emotions from within the human psyche which normal music does not. These are not the emotions of enjoyment or pleasure; this is the joining of knowledge and devotion.

The European music of tempered scales has only two basic intervals viz:- the whole tone and the semitone. Hence most of the smaller ranges shown above are inaccessible to music based on the tempered system of notes. This is the reason that altering Turkish and Sufi music in the way of the Ezgi-Arel system (mentioned in the next section) has created a hidden loss in the value of the traditional music used prior to 100 years ago.

Let's celebrate the 100 year anniversary by restoring this music to its original charm.

Intervals Lost in the Current use of Pythagorean Music in Turkey.

The use of the Ezgi/Arel notation system has resulted in a number of intervals being discarded as irrelevant. However this is not true to the tradition. Their motivation was semi-political where the drive was implemented to align their traditional music with a quasi-European notation system. Hence when I had lessons (meşk) with Necdet Yaşar² he explained to me how the music had been altered due to the western style theory of Turkish music, which was being taught throughout Turkey. He was not happy with this.

Any reader who wishes to listen to these historic lessons with Necdet Yaşar, please contact me and I can email the lesson recording for the Makam you wish to study. Most of the mainstream Makams have a lesson recording. Some lesser used Makams may need to combine two or more lessons. I will recommend which lessons when you let me know the Makam. The list of lesson recordings is given at the end of this paper.

There were three main notation systems devised. The Ezgi/Arel; the Rauf Yekta and the Ekrem Karadeniz. This last one has accidentals which are closer to the required number of notes in the system. The Rauf Yekta system is half way between the Ezgi/Arel and the Ekrem Karadeniz system. The Ezgi/Arel system is seriously deficient, as previously described. However it is necessary to consider the thinking behind each one.

Ezgi/Arel as previously stated were motivated by European and political reasons. Rauf Yekta was motivated by keeping to the Mevlevi way; but he seems to have assumed that a musician would have been taught by a teacher who had the benefit of the meşk system. This means that some notes which Rauf knew about, do not arise from his notation system; and he knew this. But he assumed the musician would know how to play the correct intonation to accord with the Makam. Hence it is not correct to label the Rauf Yekta system as being deficient. Ekrem on the other hand foresaw that in the future musicians would be trying to play the music entirely from notation, not from imitating a teacher or trained musician. Hence his notation system attempts to get as close as possible to the correct notes to be played. Not easy using the European five line staff system.

Ratio	Exact Commas	No. used	Status
3:1	84	84	
5:3	39.06	39	
7:5	25.72	26	lost
9:7	19.22	19 1/3	lost
11:9	15.34	15 1/3	lost
13:11	12.77	13	
15:13	10.94	11	lost
23:21	6.96	7	lost
25:23	6.38	6 2/3	lost
27:25	5.88	6	lost
31:29	5.10	5	
39:37	4.02	4	

The table to the left shows the main intervals which are now generally lost when playing from Ezgi/Arel notation system; unless a teacher knows differently and instructs the student how to get the correct intervals. Readers will note that the table is all intervals made from odd numbers. But there is one Just Intonation interval which is also lost. It is the ratio 7:6. This is 12 commas. It may be argued that the intervals 13:11 or 15:13 could be used. However, the beauty of the Segah Makam is in the use of the interval from rast note to segah note; which is the interval 5:4 (the natural third). One comma flatter than two whole tones. If the two whole tone interval was used instead it would not feel like Segah

Makam. When Necdet Yaşar's hearing was tested in Washington University USA, it was discovered that he could distinguish small fractions of one comma. This ability is necessary for musicians who wish to play Sufi or Mevlevi music. Most of the lost intervals listed above would make a big difference to the power and magic which can arise from Mevlevi Ayin music. If the Makams used for the healing process used by the Seljucks and

² When discussing my research with Necdet he called me "The Sherlock Holmes of Turkish Music."

the Ottomans in their Darüŝŝifas, were used with incorrect intervals, it is likely that their healing power would not arise. Similarly the power to heal the soul through Mevlevi music does not arise if the correct intervals are not used.

So this loss is significant. However it is true to say that playing the traditional music with some missing intervals will not give a dissonant experience and is not wrong where the audience only wish a pleasant experience. But it is lacking in the charm and beauty of the original sound of traditional Turkish music.

Conclusion

It is clear that music has been a part of civilisation for many thousands of years. Great people like Pythagoras have elevated the status of music as a powerful healing agent for human life in body, mind and soul. All things deteriorate with destructive power of time. For music this may be due to political or religious reasons. Also reasons of convenience often mean that traditions are altered. In the case of music the losses or deterioration can also be due to loss of contact with the authentic reasons and methods of playing.

At least two factors (1) The Mevlevi tradition being centred in Turkey - Konya & Istanbul, being the main centres; and (2) The span of the Ottoman Empire throughout the middle east; many Ottoman Makams spread to Arabic speaking nations. Arabic music has suffered a similar fate as described in this document, due to the introduction of a quarter-tone system. This was dividing the 12 tone tempered European system into quarters of a European whole tone. The correct sound of their original Makams is now lost in main stream music. Yet in rural areas it is likely the traditional Makams are played. Baron Der Langer listed all the Arabic Makams in his treatise; he used ¼ tones of European scales to do so. Hence in his system many intervals were also lost.

In both cases, Turkish and Arabic, it is the intervention of the European idea of the tempered 12 tone system which has done the damage. The whole concept that things European are superior needs to be challenged. From what this document describes it should be clear that where music is concerned European music is the one which is actually **“primitive”** not Ottoman music as stated by the political regime of the 1920s. This is clear when compared to the advanced requirements placed on composers and musicians by correct application of Pythagorean intervals and tetrachords. The European use of many simultaneous notes and melodies; and large numbers of musicians is a typical concept of many European so called developments; bigger is better according to them. Not true of Pythagorean music. It is this European idea which has also infected the Mevlevi sema ritual, now performed only as a tourist show, it has far too many of both whirlers and musicians for it to be called truly Mevlevi. See my paper “Mevlevi Music and Whirling”.

List of Makam Lesson mp3s Available on Request

If you think you already know a Makam, you may get some surprises with these.

Acem	Acem Aŝîrân	Acem Kurdi	Acem Püselik	Arazbâr	Arazbâr Püselik	Bestenigâr		
Bayatî	Bayatî Arabân	Bayatî Aŝîrân	Çârgâh	Dilkeŝide	Dügâh	Evcârâ	Evc	Ferahnâk
Ferahfezâ	Gerdâniye	Gülizâr	Hicaz Group	Hicâzkâr	Hicâz Zirgüle	Hisâr	Hisâr Püselik	
Hüseyini	Hüseyini Aŝîrân	Hüzzâm	Irak	Isfahân	Isfahânek	Kürdi	Kürdili Hicâzkâr	
Karcıgar	Mâhûr	Mâye	Muhayyer	Muhayer Kürdi	Müsteâr	Muhayyer Sünbüle		
Nevâ	Nev-eser	Nihâvent	Nihâvent-i-Kebir	Nikrîz	Niŝâbürek	Niŝâbûr	Nühüft	
Püselik Aŝîrân	Penggâh	Pesendide	Püselik	Rast	Râhatülervâh	Rehâvî	Revnaknümâ	
Rûy-î-Irak	Sabâ	Sabâ Püselik	Sabâ Zenzeme	Sâzkâr	Segâh	Ŗedd-i-arabân	Ŗehnâz	
Ŗehnâz Püselik	Ŗevk-Efzâ	Ŗevk-u Tarab	Sultânî Yegâh	Sûz-i dil	Sûz-i dilârâ	Sûzinâk		
Tâhir	Tarz-ı Nevîn	Uŝŝak	Yegâh	Zirgüleli Sûzinâk	Zavil			

**The author and his three children with the Mevlevi Çelebi
The Çelebi Sıtkı Öztürün was a holy man. A direct descendent of Mevlana.**

Mevlevi Sema at Çelebi Sıtkı Öztürün's home in Göstepe - Kadıköy - Istanbul 1987

Gönül Sıtkı Alan Andrew

Andrew Sıtkı Gönül

Relaxing at Çelebi Sıtkı Öztürün's home in Göstepe 1986

Tansy Gülsüm Andrew Alan Sıtkı Mary

My son Andrew with Sıtkı

Playing and singing ilahiler at Sıtkı's home 1986

Gülsüm Sıtkı Alan Andrew Gönül

At Nezih Uzel's home Üsküdar 1985

Nezih Tansy Alan

Gülsüm was Sıtkı's sister. Gönül was a Mevlevi family friend.

The above Mevlevi were my teachers of the Mevlevi way, and I should include my Sheikh Resuhi Baykara, not well enough to visit the Çelebi at that time.

Below are my teachers of music and its relevance in philosophy. Without these people and many others in Turkey, my journey into Mevlevi music would not have been possible.

Pythagoras the Mystic

Many centuries ago there lived a great teacher who was part of an ancient line of gurus. For nearly forty years he travelled extensively and studied at the feet of many masters. Eventually, he founded a community centred on an ashram where he advocated a contemplative, vegetarian lifestyle, taught the doctrine of reincarnation and trained his followers in sacred knowledge aimed at uniting the human soul with the Divine through mathematics and music. His biographers attribute miraculous abilities to him, including the ability to mentally perceive the deepest structures of cosmic life. No! Not an Indian mystic but Pythagoras of Samos, a Greek who was the main founder of many aspects of the European way of life.

Pythagoras is generally accepted to be one of the most significant fountainheads of Western thought. This includes diet, medicine, music, art, education mathematics, philosophy and politics. None of these would have taken the shape they did in the Western world without Pythagoras' discoveries and his influence. His teachings were in tune with the thinking of India and the East. No full understanding of European history is possible without an appreciation of the thoughts and influence of this first Western scientist and philosopher. The ideas he set in motion were among the most potent in modern history. Yet of all the founders of the Western tradition, Pythagoras is by far the least known. He played a pivotal role in transmitting the wisdom of ancient traditions to the modern world.

Personal Life

As with many figures from antiquity, facts about Pythagoras' life are sketchy. He is said to be one of those divine men of whom history knows least because his life was transfigured into legend; like his contemporary the Buddha. Nevertheless, a number of early writers have left us biographical information from which we can reconstruct his story.

Pythagoras was born on the Greek island of Samos around 569 BCE. Miraculous events surrounded his life from the very beginning. Legend holds that he was the son of Apollo, the Hellenic God of music and learning, and his birth was foretold by the oracle at Delphi. His early years were spent studying at all the centres of scientific and sacred learning in Greece and the eastern Mediterranean. Eventually, he made his way to Egypt, where for over twenty years in the temples he absorbed the Egyptians' knowledge of mathematics, music and medicine and their mystical teachings regarding the soul and the stages of its evolution.

After the Persians overran Egypt, the Persian magi recognised his learning and development and he was taken into their confidence. He became a student of their equally ancient mystery school. Pythagoras was also subject to other influences during that time, and probably undertook further travels. Some writers believe he actually went as far as India; others accept that he studied and absorbed in some form the Vedic philosophy of ancient India, which was known in Persia at that time.

His Way

His teaching began in earnest at the age of 56, when he returned from his travels to Greece. Later he relocated to the city of Kroton, a Greek settlement in southern Italy. Here he established a philosophical community which was to become known as the Pythagorean brotherhood. Entry into Pythagoras' community, essentially an ashram, required a lengthy and rigorous examination. For the members of his brotherhood, the greatest goal of wisdom was attaining to the Divine. For this, Pythagoras recommended a highly disciplined lifestyle in a loving community. His philosophy is behind that of Socrates, Plato and other Greeks.

He taught his followers that the soul is immortal and that after death it migrates into other animate bodies. To the Pythagoreans, the greatest love (philia) was that of wisdom (sophia). Thus Pythagoras was the first Western philosopher (philia + sophia). He taught the power of music used as a medicine to treat diseases of the body and its value in the cleansing of the intellect and soul; including the final unification of the soul with its creator.

See the book "Divine Harmony - The Life and Teachings of Pythagoras" ISBN 978-0965377454

Master Musician and Tanbur Virtuoso Necdet Yaşar

Not fully recognised in Turkey until 1988, Necdet Yaşar was a master tanbur player of Turkish Classical music and in 1991 was honoured as a Distinguished National Artist. Considered one of the finest instrumentalists in Turkish music in the second half of 20th century, he is a virtuoso on the tanbur. Inspired by the mystical tanbur master Meşut Cemil Bey, he studied and played under him for 30 years as the principal student of Meşut; who was the preeminent tanbur player of his time and the son of the legendary Tanburi Cemil Bey, the tanbur and kemençe virtuoso who can trace his lineage back through the centuries to the greatest players of the Ottoman courts.

Necdet Yaşar knew all aspects of the Turkish musical repertory: classical, Sufi and modern. Acknowledged as the grand master of the Turkish tanbur, he developed techniques to produce a louder sound on the relatively quiet musical instrument. Unrivalled at playing taksim, Yaşar was also famed for his subtle renditions of the composed peşrev and saz semai and renowned for his technical knowledge of the Makam system. In particular the intricate distinctions of melodic progression and microtonal intonation. His improvisations display rich and amazing modulations, masterfully employed transpositions, an advanced technique and, of course, his talent in creating impressive melodies avoiding stereotyped musical phrases. Truly, Necdet Yaşar was a poet of the tanbur, who recited Makamic verses.

He met Alan Wenham-Prosser in August 1981 who shared a master – pupil relationship for almost three decades; and taught Alan and his daughter Tansy more than 70 Makams in great detail along with a method to decipher the Makams in the Mevlevi Ayinler.

Necdet has toured throughout the world as a concert artist and ambassador of Turkish classical music, performing in the UK, Europe, East Asia and North America. Yaşar founded the Istanbul State Turkish Music Ensemble in 1988 and was the director until retiring in 1995. He passed away in May 2017 at age 87.

For more details go to https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Necdet_Yaşar

There is a full “Biography of Necdet Yaşar by Gonca Tokuz”, 2009, ISBN 978-605-60518-0-7

Not easy to find. Maybe limited numbers available – mostly in Turkish.

Made up of separate articles from family, friends, his students and colleagues.

But Gonca knew nothing about my connection with Necdet. Neither did most Turks.

Printed by Necdet’s son Ali at his printing works – Brainstorm Press. He gave me a copy.